

Experimentation on a Wireless Multi-domain Deterministic Network: the SLICES-Madrid Approach

David Rico-Menendez, Pablo Picazo-Martínez, Carlos Barroso-Fernández, Alejandro Calvillo-Fernandez, Constantine Ayimba, Antonio de la Oliva, Carlos J. Bernardos, Susruth Sudhakaran, Rafael Rosales and Dave Cavalcanti.

Abstract—The advent of the Fifth Generation Mobile Network (5G) deployments and the anticipation of the Sixth Generation Mobile Network (6G) have spurred a concerted effort towards defining new network and application services that harness the potential of these technologies. One of these key technologies is deterministic networking, which has emerged as a focal point, offering reliability, time sensitivity, and predictability, crucial for supporting critical services and applications. In this article, we present our tailored extensions to the Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies (SLICES)-Madrid testbed to support multi-domain deterministic communications research, enabling the union of different technology-specific deterministic networking solutions, namely Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) 802.11, IEEE 802.1 Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), and Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) 5G domains, over an Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) Deterministic Networking (DetNet) overlay data plane. Our endeavor aims to provide a realistic infrastructure for developing the next generation of deterministic services. Key contributions include the design, deployment, and performance characterization of the multi-domain data plane, along with its integration into the SLICES-Madrid site. This article offers insights into the design, implementation, and implications of a multi-domain deterministic data plane, providing valuable contributions to the research community and laying the groundwork for future community experimentation in the field of deterministic networking.

Index Terms—DetNet, TSN, multi-domain, WCT, SLICES

I. INTRODUCTION

We are currently in the midst of a significant push to define novel network services that exploit the potential of Fifth Generation Mobile Network (5G) deployments and the emergence of Sixth Generation Mobile Network (6G). In this context, provisioning networks with deterministic characteristics is gaining substantial attention. A deterministic network is distinguished by its reliability, time sensitivity, and predictability, offering crucial support to critical services and other applications requiring guarantees on delay, jitter, and packet loss.

The authors are with the Department of Telematics Engineering, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid; and Intel Labs. E-mail: {drico, papicazo, cbarroso, acalvill}@pa.uc3m.es, {ayconsta, aoliva, cjb}@it.uc3m.es, {susruth.sudhakaran, rafael.rosales, dave.cavalcanti}@intel.com.

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The significance of deterministic development within contemporary networks is underscored by numerous initiatives across various standardization bodies in recent years. Noteworthy examples include Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) 802.1 Time Sensitive Networking (TSN), which has been delineating time-sensitive communications at the bridge level (primarily compatible with Ethernet), IEEE 802.11's discussions on determinism within IEEE 802.11be (Wi-Fi 7) and its pivotal role in IEEE 802.11bn (the upcoming Wi-Fi 8, also referred to as ultra-reliable communications), and Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)'s definition of the time-sensitive communication subsystem.

The concept of determinism is gradually permeating the design of modern networks. However, envisioning a future where deterministic connected services are ubiquitous necessitates transcending technology-specific silos. The imperative of interconnecting these disparate technologies to construct a Layer-3, Internet-wide (to a certain extent), multi-domain deterministic network is being addressed by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)'s Deterministic Networking (DetNet) group (Sect. II).

This article introduces a first-of-its-class, multi-domain deterministic experimental platform, leveraging a DetNet-based data plane that integrates IEEE 802.11, IEEE 802.1 TSN, and 3GPP domains providing researchers with a realistic network infrastructure for developing next-generation deterministic services. Given the complexity of the task, we leverage the capabilities of the Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies (SLICES) Wireless Community Testbed (WCT), expanding the SLICES-Madrid node (Sec. III) to support deterministic communications. This involves several open research and standardization challenges, such as: (i) ensuring that deterministic conditions can be achieved when traversing multiple technology and/or administrative domains using a common data plane; (ii) assessing that Wi-Fi and cellular (5G) technologies are capable of offering a degree of determinism that is good enough to meet the requirements of a realistic use case; and, (iii) provide the research community with tools and experimental platforms that can be leveraged to validate use cases and evaluate new mechanisms flexibly and openly.

Our main contributions to the research community include:

- Designing and evaluating the performance of modified IEEE 802.11 and 3GPP domains to enhance deterministic

Fig. 1: SLICES Madrid configurable 5G testbed.

traffic (Sec. IV). This involves exploiting enhancements provided by Intel for IEEE 802.11, implementing IEEE 802.1AS and IEEE 802.1Qbv over AX210 Wi-Fi wireless cards [1], and implementing a traffic shaping mechanism coupled with prudent modulation coding scheme (MCS) selection (robust against channel noise to minimize re-transmissions) for 3GPP. This addresses the challenge (i) identified before.

- Implementing a multi-domain data plane that integrates the aforementioned technologies (Sec. V) – namely, experimental IEEE 802.11 with TSN extensions, a 3GPP Rel-15 domain-based and commercial IEEE 802.1 TSN switches, interconnected at Layer-3 by a DetNet overlay data plane in SLICES-Madrid, addressing challenge (ii).
- Validating the value of the deployed WCT for future experimenters in need of a heterogeneous deterministic-enabled multi-domain platform, as proved by the obtained results (Sec. VI), addressing the challenge (iii).
- Providing a heterogeneous multi-domain platform to experimenters, supporting research in deterministic networking, and enabling the exploration of integrated technologies.

II. MULTI-DOMAIN DETERMINISTIC NETWORKING

A. Motivation

We believe 6G networks must transition from traditional service models to become deterministic, meaning reliable, time-sensitive, and predictable. In this new network concept, flows can request special treatment for bounded latency, low jitter, and high reliability, including resource availability, low packet loss, and failure resiliency. Applications benefiting from such networking include audio and video streaming, industrial automation, cloud robotics, IoT, and digital twins. Reliable information delivery is crucial for these applications. The business need for deterministic networks is borne out by major standards-developing organizations designing new deterministic approaches. However, there is no holistic End-to-End (E2E) programmable service architecture for deterministic services across multiple technologies and domains. Projects

such as PREDICT-6G¹ and 6G-DATADRIVEN² as well as the IETF DetNet working group seek to address this gap.

For instance, in industrial automation, modern manufacturing is facilitated by wireless communication, where determinism is crucial for ensuring predictable and reliable operations. This is particularly important when offloading logic and intelligence of moving machinery to edge or cloud infrastructure, then using digital twins to monitor, control, and optimize their operations. Ensuring low latency and high reliability across multiple domains (e.g., Ethernet, Wi-Fi, 5G) is essential in scenarios with distributed sites, requiring trustworthy connectivity between robots and control infrastructure which a single networking technology cannot reliably achieve.

B. IETF Deterministic Networking

To efficiently integrate different technological domains and provide a single E2E deterministic data plane, we utilize recent developments of the IETF DetNet working group. DetNet focuses on deterministic data paths operating over bridged Layer-2 and routed Layer-3 segments. These paths provide bounds on reordering, latency, loss, packet delay variation (jitter), and high reliability. DetNet creates a Layer-3 overlay data plane on top of the technological domains and elicits the deterministic characteristics of each.

The DetNet data plane architecture splits functionality into service and forwarding sub-layers. The service sub-layer is used to provide DetNet service protection and reordering. The forwarding sub-layer implements traffic engineering mechanisms and provides congestion protection (low loss, assured latency, and limited out-of-order delivery). A given forwarding sub-layer may have capabilities that are unavailable on other forwarding sub-layers.

According to the DetNet architecture, end-systems connected to a DetNet domain encapsulate packets according to their service requirements; *edge DetNet nodes* operate in

¹Deliverables D1.2, D2.2 & D3.2 on deterministic multidomain from PREDICT6G at <https://predict-6g.eu/deliverables/>

²6G-DATADRIVEN 04 focuses on a multi-technology connectivity layer for Industry 4.0 <https://unica6g.it.uc3m.es/6g-datadriven/entregables/>

both service and forwarding sub-layers to provide assigned functionalities to incoming packets and *transit DetNet nodes* (which may be unaware of the special requirements of the DetNet service sub-layer) provide Quality of Service (QoS) capabilities needed by the traffic flows. The IETF DetNet architecture, though out of the scope of current standardization efforts, also considers other components such as a control and management plane. The latter programs the data plane of DetNet nodes so they can provide the per-flow QoS while the former carries out operations, administration, and management mechanisms required to maintain a deterministic network.

In subsequent sections, we detail our extensions to the SLICES-Madrid testbed to support multi-domain deterministic communications by leveraging the IETF DetNet data plane over wired TSN, enhanced Wi-Fi TSN and an open-source based 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) and core.

III. SLICES-MADRID: WIRELESS COMMUNITY TESTBED FOR ADVANCED MOBILE NETWORKS EXPERIMENTATION

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) program is a strategic instrument to provide competitive and open access to high-quality research infrastructures. SLICES [2] is the first ESFRI infrastructure specifically supporting research in Information and Communication Technologies and has been included in its Roadmap since 2021.

SLICES-Spain is the Spanish national node with two constituent sites; the first in Madrid (hosted at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid & IMDEA Networks) and the second in the Basque Country. SLICES-Madrid focuses on Beyond 5G and 6G research, exploiting the experience gained from over 7 years of activities in the complementary 5TONIC open co-innovation and co-creation laboratory.

SLICES—Madrid presents an open-source, configurable end-to-end 5G testbed³— cf. Fig. 1. It offers Open5GS, OAI-5GC, and free5GC as configurable core network solutions to external researchers. Moreover, it provides Software Radio Systems and OpenAirInterface5G as radio solutions with different cell configurations, allowing the deployment of a Next Generation Node B (gNB) in different bands and numerologies. As User Equipment (UE), researchers can use industrial 5G hats, commercial phones or an UE emulator, with a capacity of up to 56 UEs.

IV. EVALUATION OF EACH DETNET DOMAIN

In this section, we explain how we have extended the SLICES-Madrid WCT to support deterministic communications across multiple technological domains, namely an experimental Wi-Fi TSN domain, a commercial wired-TSN domain, and an OpenAirInterface (OAI)-based 3GPP domain modified to provide deterministic capabilities.

Fig. 2 shows the domain encapsulation of the packets following Multiprotocol Label Switching (MPLS) over Internet Protocol (IP) and User Datagram Protocol (UDP) Detnet Dataplane – marked green for 3GPP, orange for wired TSN and blue for wireless TSN. In addition, we build an E2E DetNet

tunnel that uses codewords and service labels to distinguish different flows, marked with red and black arrows.

1) *Wi-Fi TSN*: The IEEE 802.1 Task Group defines TSN capabilities to enable time synchronization and deterministic latency in local area networks. Although the initial focus was on adding determinism to standard Ethernet-based links, TSN tools have been extended to wireless links supported by the 802.11 MAC/PHY capabilities, such as Fine Timing Measurement (FTM) and scheduling [3]. The Wi-Fi TSN capabilities considered in the testbed include time synchronization based on the IEEE 802.1AS Generalized Precision Time Protocol (gPTP) operating over 802.11 FTM as defined in the media-specific clause 12 of the 802.1AS specification. We make use of a software implementation of the IEEE 802.1Qbv time-aware scheduling to create protected windows for time-critical traffic by blocking non-critical traffic during such windows, thereby providing better control of the latency in the 802.11 MAC layer as demonstrated in [3].

Our Wi-Fi TSN testbed is composed of two Intel NUC equipped with AX210 Wi-Fi 6/6E chipsets with FTM capability, one operating as Station (STA) and the other as a software-enabled Access Point (AP). The 802.1AS implementation uses a modified Linux Precision Time Protocol (PTP) that includes support for 802.11 and leverages the FTM implementation in the AX210 to compute the synchronization offset between the AP as time grandmaster and the STA as time follower. The 802.1Qbv implementation, well-suited for use with a soft AP, maps traffic streams to two queues (one time-critical and the other best-effort) using the Linux Queue Discipline (Qdisc)⁴ features and open/close the queues based on the requirements of the traffic streams. A schedule is set at configuration time to protect time-critical streams from interfering with best-effort traffic. Though our implementation uses two queues, there is no loss in generality, as it can be easily extended to the four independent QoS queues supported in Wi-Fi to isolate the time-critical traffic.

In the experimental evaluation of our Wi-Fi TSN testbed, we conducted a series of measurements focusing on the impact of varying traffic loads on deterministic and Best Effort (BE) traffic. The experiments were carried out in a controlled environment using a hardware time stamper and an isolation chamber (omitted in Fig. 2 for clarity) to minimize external interference and avoid Wi-Fi shared channel access. Our measurements specifically targeted the performance of the IEEE 802.1Qbv enhanced transmission selection mechanism, which we configured to recognize deterministic flows within a total cycle time of 1 ms, dedicating 25% of this time exclusively to the deterministic traffic queue gate.

In our experiments, given that the wireless link supports up to 110 Mbps, we consistently injected constant BE background traffic at a rate of 100 Mbps, reducing available link capacity to 10 Mbps. Deterministic traffic flows, each requiring 2 Mbps, were incrementally introduced until reaching a total of ten flows. The latter, together with BE traffic, exceeded the link capacity (reaching a total 20 Mbps connectivity of TSN plus 100 Mbps background BE traffic). In a non-deterministic

³More information available in <https://www.slices-madrid.eu/blueprint-5g-research-infrastructure/>.

⁴<https://tldp.org/HOWTO/Traffic-Control-HOWTO/classless-qdiscs.html/>

Fig. 2: Logical (top) and actual (bottom) views of the SLICES-Madrid deterministic multi-domain testbed.

Fig. 3: Per-packet delays in Wi-Fi TSN domain, for one, two, five, and ten flows of 2 Mbps deterministic traffic, and their corresponding background 100 Mbps BE traffic (inset).

environment, TSN traffic would suffer from high delays and jitter or even packet losses in the experiments with five and ten flows. We remark that with only two queues implemented, all TSN flows will share the same critical queue, while the rest of the BE traffic will be mapped into the non-priority queue.

As depicted in the Experimental Cumulative Density Function (ECDF) in Fig. 3, even when the cumulative traffic approached and surpassed the Wi-Fi link’s capacity, the deterministic traffic maintained its integrity with stable delay, as expected. We also measured zero packet loss for the deterministic traffic. In contrast, the BE traffic experienced increased delays and was impacted by IEEE 802.1Qbv actions to prioritize deterministic flows and uphold the determinism of the network. This behavior underscores the effectiveness of the IEEE 802.1Qbv mechanism in protecting critical traffic under conditions of network congestion, a key requirement for real-time deterministic applications dependent on Wi-Fi.

2) *Commercial wired TSN*: Our wired TSN domain uses RELY-TSN-BRIDGE⁵, a four-port switch, tailored to critical sectors including railway, aerospace, automotive and industrial automation. It is composed of four such switches, each of which ensures network reliability within this domain and supports the IEEE 802.11Qbv enhancement for scheduled traffic. Additionally, these switches also support Frame Replication and Elimination for Reliability (FRER) further bolstering our network’s robustness against potential frame losses and ensuring higher reliability. The device is equipped with an onboard Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA) offering a high-speed network switch and precise PTP timestamping capabilities. This setup is supported by a multicore central processing unit (CPU) that hosts an autonomous software application, enhancing overall system responsiveness and functional flexibility.

3) *3GPP*: In the 3GPP domain, we deployed OAI, an open-source RAN + 5G Core solution. The radio side is composed of a Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) that raises a physical cell on n78 with 20 MHz bandwidth, and the core hosts each network function on different docker containers. For the UE, we integrated a Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) terminal with a Linux host to establish a configurable network interface via Linux kernel. To reduce interference, during experimentation, we put both USRP antennas and UE in an isolated box, making use of attenuators to emulate a real propagation scenario.

Current 3GPP open-source networks lack tools to ensure determinism. To overcome this fact, we implemented a traffic shaper on the Linux Qdisc combined with an adaptive MCS selection on the radio side. Regarding the shaper, we set boundaries for different traffic classes using QoS Class Id-

⁵<https://www.relyum.com/web/rely-tsn-bridge-3/>

Fig. 4: Distribution of per-packet latency in the 3GPP domain. Left: for deterministic traffic with background BE traffic exceeding the link capacity (deterministic traffic is unaffected). Right: for deterministic traffic using MCS 3. Inset: for BE traffic (delay is significantly higher when BE traffic is above the capacity).

tifiers (QCI). This allows us to manage all traffic considered non-deterministic, shaping it according to the link throughput available.

Typically, in 3GPP systems, the default MCS algorithm is designed to optimize throughput by selecting a MCS that tolerates a block error rate (BLER) of up to 10% for a given radio channel. To ensure bounded latency and eliminate Automatic Repeat reQuest (ARQ) retransmissions, we adjusted the MCS below the channel capabilities to achieve a BLER of 0%, thereby reaching over-the-air error-free transmissions at the cost of reducing the bandwidth available.

To validate our approach, we tested with different MCSs while handling deterministic traffic loads of 1 Mbps alongside three BE traffic scenarios. First, we generated combined deterministic and BE traffic below the radio link’s capacity; then, exactly matching the radio link’s capacity; and, finally, exceeding the radio link’s capacity to verify that the BE traffic does not compromise the integrity of the deterministic traffic.

We apply this procedure using four distinct MCS⁶: MCS 3 and 9, which correspond to Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) modulation with 251/1024 and 679/1024 coding rates, respectively; and MCS 12 and 18, which corresponds to 16-Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM) with 434/1024 coding rate, and 64-QAM with 466/1024 coding rate, respectively. Each experiment was conducted over five minutes with constant background BE traffic.

Fig. 4-(left) illustrates the latency observed for MCS 3 with 1 Mbps deterministic traffic and three types of BE traffic. Given that the link capacity for this MCS is 5 Mbps, we generated 2, 4, and 10 Mbps of BE traffic, respectively. Our experiments show that BE traffic has no noticeable effect on the latency or packet loss of deterministic traffic. Fig. 4-(right) shows the impact of MCS modifications on deterministic traffic under congestion conditions where traffic exceeds the radio capacity. Using MCS 3 safeguards latency below 20 ms with a consistently observed BLER of 0%. Conversely, MCS 9 and 12

exhibit increases in latency as their forward error correction is not as robust prompting re-transmissions. However, they also experience a BLER below 10^{-3} . Increasing to MCS 18 results in a compromised latency due to the channel state’s inability to maintain low BLER thereby triggering retransmissions which increase latency. Finally, Fig. 4-(right inset) depicts how BE traffic is impacted, particularly when operating above the radio link capacity leading to queue overflows.

We can conclude that the features implemented within the 3GPP domain significantly enhance both reliability and determinism, effectively bounding the latency of deterministic traffic for time-critical applications, even in scenarios with dense background traffic.

V. INTEGRATION OF MULTIPLE DOMAINS LEVERAGING IETF DETNET

As stated in section II-B, the DetNet working group [4] is developing solutions for deterministic Layer-3 data paths. In this section, we present our DetNet based architecture. The DetNet data plane solution divides functionality into service and forwarding sub-layers. The latter carries information to reach the next hop, and provides QoS functions to satisfy flow requirements, for example, through queuing methods, or relying on the assistance of the underlying Layer-2 connectivity. The Service sub-layer provides further functionalities such as Packet Replication, Elimination and Ordering Function (PREOF). To achieve all this, DetNet encodes specific flow attributes (flow identity and sequence number) in packets. Different technologies can be used as DetNet data planes. We opt for MPLS over UDP/IP, as it allows us to fully implement the forwarding and service sub-layer functionalities of the DetNet data plane.

Leveraging DetNet, we integrate multiple domains by making the nodes at the boundaries of the different domains work as gateways with additional functionalities. We consider three main DetNet functions: forwarding, for the transmission of packet flows between domains; encapsulation, and decapsulation. The path across domains is computed globally, taking into account the service requirements and the capabilities of each domain. Notice that the service sub-layer can implement PREOF to meet requirements that individual domains cannot handle on their own. This function enhances deterministic capabilities by replicating packets, eliminating duplicates, and ordering them before exiting the system to minimize jitter. We remark that in our experiments, we statically configure these paths *a priori*.

An operating system kernel inherently lacks determinism due to unpredictable scheduling and interrupt handling, which can introduce latency and jitter into network packet processing. This means building a standalone solution for DetNet on non-specific TSN and open-source hardware poses significant challenges. To overcome this, we have developed a solution using eXpress Data Path (XDP) technology, a high-performance, programmable network data path in the Linux kernel. By leveraging XDP, we can intercept and process packets at the earliest point in the software stack, bypassing the kernel’s networking stack entirely. This approach not only minimizes

⁶3GPP TS 38.214 version 15.2.0 Release 15-Table 5.1.3.1-1 https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/138200_138299/138214/15.02.00_60/ts_138214v150200p.pdf.

latency by eliminating unnecessary kernel overhead but also ensures more predictable and deterministic packet handling. These benefits are crucial to providing the robust and efficient packet management necessary for our advanced research and development in deterministic networking.

The 3GPP domain is integrated as a bridge and the DetNet nodes connected to it act as the Network and Device Side translators (Network-Side TSN Translator and Device-Side TSN Translator), as defined by 3GPP specifications. This facilitates the overall E2E functionality by hiding the internal 3GPP specific procedures.

VI. END TO END EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present the E2E analysis of our DetNet multi-domain experiments carried out on the extended SLICES-Madrid testbed. Our illustrative use case, of multi-domain deterministic communications, is that of a Digital Twin (DT) used to control a robot dog located at a remote production plant. The DT of the robot dog provides a real-time virtual representation, enabling precise monitoring and control over its actions. Communication between the DT application and the actual robot dog is enabled by a 5G network that provides connectivity between the company headquarters and the remote manufacturing plant where the robot is located. Commands issued by the DT travel through the 5G network, transition through a wired network, and finally reach the robot dog via a Wi-Fi AP. The critical and time-sensitive traffic for transmitting these commands reflect real TSN traffic characteristics. We configure the control loop to send a packet every 10 ms resulting in periodic traffic of 10 Kbps. The messages, specifically the "HighCmd" commands, are essential for transmitting real-time control instructions to the robot, ensuring that it responds promptly and accurately to the commands issued by the control system.

To meet the requirements of the use case, we configured the domains as follows: Wi-Fi and wired deterministic 802.1Qbv implementations have a cycle time of 1 ms, being a quarter of the time dedicated to deterministic traffic; 3GPP domain is configured with MCS 3, as it provides the lowest latency and jitter, ensuring a BLER of 0% on the radio link. In addition, we configure our dynamic input throttling agent for the BE traffic.

We conducted our experiments with varying traffic loads, ranging from one to ten flows of the deterministic traffic defined earlier, accompanied by background best-effort BE traffic. With one TSN flow the traffic is below channel capacity, and we gradually increase the TSN flows until we exceed it. For each configuration (one, two, five, and ten flows), we captured every packet with nanosecond precision over a five-minute duration. Each experiment was repeated three times to ensure the consistency of the results. The configuration of each domain remained consistent with the setup used in the previous per-domain performance evaluation. This configuration was used to evaluate the ability of the extended network to handle significant variations in traffic load while still prioritizing time-sensitive communications crucial for the operation of the robot dog in a real-time industrial setting.

(a) E2E delay for deterministic traffic

(b) E2E delay for BE traffic

Fig. 5: Distribution of the delay per packet of deterministic traffic in E2E scenario.

Fig. 5a shows the latency distribution per packet for one, two, five, and ten TSN flows. The results indicate that all TSN flows are delivered within 18 ms across the E2E, which is coherent with the sum of the single domain latencies. However, the E2E throughput is limited by the 3GPP network. The latency of BE traffic increases noticeably when the total traffic (TSN + BE) exceeds the network's capacity, see – Fig. 5b. This happens with two TSN flows and above, as the total traffic surpasses the network's capacity, the BE traffic queues increase. When the queues are filled, the throttler is triggered, thereby increasing the experienced latency and packet loss.

VII. COMPARISON WITH OTHER PLATFORMS

This work introduces a multi-domain WCT that provides latency-bounded capabilities over a heterogeneous E2E DetNet based network. While there exist other multi-domain testbeds, they do not support multi-domain determinism. This integration aims to provide researchers with a robust platform for experimental validation of deterministic network services across various domains. This approach mirrors the flexibility seen in platforms such as the one described in [5]. This framework integrates COTS hardware with open-source tools to build an adaptable hardware set-up for industrial automation. Other works focus on open cloud testbed for TSN [6]. Some platforms utilize advanced hardware features that support precise time-synchronization and fine-gradient scheduling, allowing the control plane to operate in real-time. The platform presented in [7] advances these concepts by integrating a fully programmable controller designed to manage TSN across wired and wireless domains, trying to address the challenge of extending TSN capabilities beyond

traditional wired networks. However, none of these innovations provide seamless determinism across multiple domains.

The approach taken in [8] for addressing the challenge of wireless TSN focuses on the management of scheduled traffic. A comparable approach can be found in [9] for taking a step forward merging TSN with 5G infrastructure, thus supporting Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) applications. Yet, these advancements still do not bridge the gap between multiple domains.

The advancement of wireless communications technologies is supported by several large-scale testbeds. *POWDER* [10] offers a city-scale outdoor environment, promoting wireless experiments under real-world conditions. *COSMOS* [11] specializes in ultra-high bandwidth and low latency communications, emphasizing 5G advancements. *AERPAW* [12] on integrated aerial systems with wireless networks, facilitating aerial and ground-based technological evaluations in North Carolina state. *ARA* [13] promotes research across the U.S. on novel technologies and spectrum-sharing protocols for rural areas. Lastly, *COLOSSEUM* [14] stands out as the largest wireless network emulator, capable of simulating complex urban settings and supporting experiments with up to 256 nodes. However, none of these large-scale testbeds supports experimental validation of TSN and deterministic services.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we have presented a multi-domain testbed that enables deterministic communication between endpoints, a critical feature for modern industrial applications. Through the integration of DetNet across diverse domains, we have not only addressed the challenges of delivering deterministic services under variable network conditions but have also developed and characterized enhancements to wireless technologies. Specifically, we have introduced a traffic shaping mechanism within an open-source 5G solution, significantly reducing re-transmissions and enhancing reliability.

Moreover, we have shown how incorporating IEEE 802.1Qbv and 802.1AS specifications in our testbed enhanced its capabilities in managing deterministic networking over Wi-Fi, enabling precise control over critical traffic and effective latency management across these domains. Our developments include a data plane that integrates multi-domain technology, addressing the gap for enhanced determinism across heterogeneous access technologies. This article not only demonstrates that these integrations are feasible, but also identifies the need for further improvements in deterministic behavior within, 3GPP as well as studies how WLAN interference can be mitigated to improve determinism.

As a contribution to the broader research and development community, we have made the 3GPP and TSN components within the SLICES framework available to the research community. This allows other researchers and developers to engage with, and further develop, these technologies. This initiative supports ongoing innovation and development in the field of deterministic networking, providing a robust platform for future research.⁷

⁷All the services offered are available in <https://www.slices-madrid.eu/>.

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David Rico got his M.Sc. in 2024 and is a Ph.D. student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Pablo Picazo-Martínez got his M.Sc. in 2022 and is a Ph.D. student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Carlos Barroso-Fernández got his M.Sc. in 2022 and is a Ph.D. student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Alejandro Calvillo-Fernández got his M.Sc. in 2024 and is a Ph.D. student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Constantine Ayimba got his M.Sc. in 2016 and his Ph.D. in 2022, is post-doctoral researcher at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Antonio de la Oliva got his M.Sc. in 2004 and his Ph.D. in 2008, is an associate professor at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Carlos J. Bernardos got his M.Sc. in 2003 and his Ph.D. in 2006 and he is a Professor at UC3M.

Susruth Sudhakaran got his BTech in 1998 and his M.Sc. in 2002, is a research scientist at Intel Corporation.

Rafael Rosales got his M.Sc. in 2010 and his Ph.D. in 2017, is a research scientist at Intel Corporation.

Dave Cavalcanti (Senior Member, IEEE) received the Ph.D. in 2006. He has been a Principal Engineer with Intel Corporation, since 2015.